

ESSENCE AND PROPERTIES OF EUPHEMISM FROM PERSPECTIVE OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Abstract:

In modern philology, whose priorities at present shift towards communicative, discursive and cognitive linguistics, the structural, semantic and pragmatic features of euphemisms are studied in new aspects, classifications of euphemisms being developed on various grounds. The way knowledge is structured in a language, "packed" into different format linguistic signs of different lengths, is one of the main issues of cognitive linguistics, the research core of which is "language as a general cognitive mechanism, as a cognitive tool a system of signs that play a role in representation (coding) and in the transformation of information.

Key words: cognitive linguistics, cognitive mechanism, cognitive tool, social convention, discursive convention, conceptual metaphor, euphemistic nominations

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Euphemisms are considered among diverse linguistic phenomena used to name various objects of reality, which they relate not directly, but indirectly, and are understood as signs of an indirect nomination, intended to code certain objects, phenomena, events or actions for various purposes (according to the characteristics of the signs). A feature of euphemisms is that the basis of their formation is the principle of secondary nomination. The principle of indirect nomination is understood as a deliberately allegorical designation of an object or the conscious use of such a naming, which indicates the object of the nomination not directly, but indirectly, describes it veiled. Nowadays, linguistics sees a resurgence of scientific interest in the problem of indirect (secondary) nomination. This might be explained by the fact that being an integrative discipline, cognitive linguistics has become a rightful part of the science of language, and has introduced its own theoretical and methodological means for a deeper study of indirect nomination. Linguistic phenomena falling into the circle of attention of indirect communication (sign formations) have previously been described fractionally from the point of view of indirect nomination. Cognitive linguistics, with its new research tools, expands significantly the empirical base of linguistics. Explication of the cognitive structure of the phenomenon under study makes it possible to reveal the logic and methods of encoding a denotatum of a euphemism. That a euphemism is a means (one of the linguistic forms) of representing knowledge in the processes of categorizing and conceptualizing the world raises no doubts among the representatives of the scientific community. However, this statement cannot serve as irrefutable

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evidence of the unique role of euphemism in creating an array of human knowledge about reality.

Thus, the thesis about euphemization as a special case of conceptual derivation formulated by Boldyrev N.N. and Aleksikova Yu.V. outlines the essence of the primary task of the euphemistic transition from an unacceptable verbal form to an appropriate one ad hoc in the context of a humanistic request, the transformation of the dramatic (semantic) component of the systemic and structural organization of human knowledge, which cannot be performed by other means of language. In modern linguistics, the question of how to describe individual fragments of the linguistic picture of the world is being raised and actively resolved. In this case, various sets of linguistic units are used as research material, which differ from each other primarily in the volume and criteria underlying their unification.

Peculiarities of interpretation of the concept of "euphemism" - The universal scientific definition of the notion of "euphemism" remains the subject of constant debate. While conducting an analytical review of the sources reflecting the current state of the study of a euphemism as a phenomenon, we have revealed the interpretive heterogeneity of the central notion (a euphemism). Both predecessors and contemporaries have carried out many researches in order to provide a thorough description and classification of euphemisms in terms of linguistic, psychological, pragmatic, stylistic, cultural and other approaches.

This work is devoted to one of not yet fully studied issues, namely, the study of a euphemism as a mental phenomenon mediated by the internal mental activity of the human mind. The sphere of interests of cognitive linguistics as far as this phenomenon is concerned includes a euphemism as a result of the synthetic unity of individual and national mentality, as well as the dynamics of social and cultural human activity, as a way to achieve harmony, when a euphemism is synthesized intentionally to meet the needs of society (social convention), by synchronizing external and internal reality ad hoc (discursive convention).

In general, being characterized by multipurpose motivational determinants (which is characteristic of all languages □ at that every single language reflecting specific cultural and national features (linguistic and cultural universals) characteristic of a particular community or ethnos the euphemism realizes an individual request within the framework of the discursive convention. The scenario of euphemistic realization reflects the dialectics of the public and the private, of the universal and the particular, of the common and the unique, of the possible and the indeed. Semiotic euphemistic representation of each individual concept is carried out through a powerful verbal resource, one of the semiotically most universal ways of conceptualization offered by the language system and speech practice.

The semiotic euphemistic substrate of the concept chosen by the Speaker appeals to a number of synonyms, lexical and semantic fields, metaphorical images, precedent names, symbols, works of art, rituals, objects of material and spiritual culture. Despite the fact that there is no exhaustive description capable of expressing the entire content of the concept, the scale of the semiotic euphemistic environment is directly related to the significance of this concept for the linguocultural community, to the axiological or theoretical value of that extra-linguistic phenomenon that is embodied in all its cognitive-semantic volume, as well as to the scale of assessments and measures which the

individual uses to evaluate the events and conditions of their own life. Under the cognitive research priority of euphemisms is the metaphor which acts as the main cognitive mechanism for the formation of euphemisms.

The conceptual metaphor has also proved to be one of the most productive ways to form euphemistic nominations, since it avoids the use of direct nomination by referring to the means of representing another concept. According to Yu.V. Aleksikova, in order to ensure that the interlocutor understands the euphemistic name, the euphemism should contain significant components of the content of the original concept.

Basic properties of euphemisms - Taking into account the above-mentioned characteristics, we suppose that in order for a lexical unit to have the status of a euphemism, it is necessary to implement three sufficient conditions for a minimum, i.e., a lexical unit must have certain properties, namely: denotative amelioration, which corresponds to the basic property of euphemism of a subjective, formal "emendation" of denotatum, improvement of meaning; semantic contensivity (strategy of morpho-syntactic coding with a transition from meaning to form), which corresponds to the basic property of veiling, □expression with a hint, semantic ambiguity, semantic reduction; and information traduction (a property of a transferred characteristic), which reflects such a basic property of a euphemism as reliability, preservation of the truth and information content of the original concept. The basic properties of a euphemism can be explicated through various elements that represent lexemes, words, phrases, which in various conditions and in their own contexts can form complex figurative structures, such as a paraphrase, antithesis, metaphor.

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